

Service Design Challenges

D4.1

Deliverable Status: PUBLIC

Partners Involved

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Deliverable Review and Approval

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Deliverable Development and Review Process

	Key Event	Delivery Deadline	Actual delivery
1	Submission of Internal Draft Deliverable to reviewers and uploading on Research Participant Portal	26/11/18	27/11/18
2	Initial Review and Comments obtained	28/11/18	28/11/18
3	Uploading of Final Deliverable on Participant Portal and submission	30/11/18	30/11/18

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Working on defining a set of Service Design Challenges for FreeWheel has been extremely stimulating. There was the chance to have a cohesive reading at all the work previously done in the various WPs, the deliverables, the internal reports. The team played all the qualitative interviews once again; going through the Stories Repository.

The main efforts were on setting a solid ground not only for the upcoming activities in the project but also for the future (and promising) exploitation of the results after the end of it.

The Service Design Challenges selected in the end, are representing a well-balanced and determined intention to hold the human-centered design approach to the core of the project.

This is the list of the Service Design Challenges. This document recollects how they were defined.

ID	Challenge	Rationale
C1	Correctly inform the potential client about service suitability before and during the registration process	It is important to create the right awareness and knowledge about the possibility of using the service before people start to enrol in the subscription process. Building the right expectations is essential for avoiding pain points and unpleasant feelings.
C2	Deliver a customized interface fully compatible with client's wheelchair to access the service 2 weeks after registration	The gap between the successful subscription and the first use of the service needs to be short. Improved mobility and independence in everyday life will ask for speed and service excellence.
C3	Have the interface safely installed on the wheelchair to use the service	Connecting a personal, and very important, device, as a wheelchair, to a new commercial device (FreeWheel module), is a key moment of the experience and needs to be achieved in the most precise and non-stressful way. Additionally, a wheelchair is a medical device and requires very strict procedures while being handled.
C4	Design the digital interface for manually driving the module	Most of the enhanced experience FreeWheel is bringing to clients is referred to the ability to interact with the module and drive it with a very low amount of physical energy and fatigue. We are relying upon digital interfaces on the smartphone, reproducing a driving interface that is, actually, a multi-level design challenge.
C5	Design the service taking into account an accompanying person	The accompanying person is a key actor in the experience and the whole service needs to shape their features accordingly to his or her presence/absence. We decided to use a specific care addressing all the service design activities related to this key stakeholder.

C6	Develop an integration enabling third-party services	Looking at FreeWheel from the service provisioning perspective and contextualising its business opportunities, we considered relevant to equip the system with the possibility of third-party integration. We want to keep the core scope of the service focussed on the mobility device, but we need to create an expanding system where new actors can provide additional features to our clients.
C7	Design proper training to drive the module both manually and autonomously, including the switching between modes	During the research phase, training for new devices has been highlighted as a pain point of the experiences, sometimes because missing, some other because it's hard to acquire an adequate level of confidence with a wheelchair (and a new module attached on it).
C8	Manage the booking interactions between the "in advance mode" and the "on-the-fly-rental"	Accordingly, to the venue and different approaches to mobility, identified in user archetypes (D2.1), the service should offer the chance to book a module in great advance (e.g. two weeks), but also at the moment, maybe directly on-site. Here comes the challenge of designing part of the service experience managing bookings in an efficient way over time, ensuring always that the client has what he.or.she needs.
C9	Ensure clients safety and proper assistance in case of devices (smartphone, module) or software (application, controller) failures	The service is for people experiencing motion limitations, and a failure could mean a very frustrating situation for them. The assistance in such a moment has a key importance and needs to be delivered in the most appropriate way.

Takeaways

The design will accommodate and satisfy a wide range of clients needs, but FreeWheel service cannot be universal. Some prospect clients will not be entitled to use the service because of their category of disability. In some cases (e.g. complete tetraplegia) client's mobility impairments obviously prevent using FreeWheel service, while in some other cases it depends and needs to be investigated on a case by case basis (e.g. incomplete tetraplegia with severe effects on hands/fingers control). The service provider's responsibility is to make sure people can use the service safely. This simple concept will enforce a protocol to define who can and who cannot use FreeWheel with as a result, possible unsatisfied and frustrated customers. This limitation is a compromise to find between safety and inclusiveness of the service and technology the Consortium is designing.

Another important positive takeaway is related to the indirect effects of implementing a FreeWheel service into a location. As outlined in the Theory of Change (D2.4), the improved experience directly provided by our service will certainly ask for new needs to be satisfied. Needs that were previously unknown or impossible to emerge in a specific location before implementing a service like FreeWheel. Just to make an example: implementing FreeWheel for the visitors of a large archaeological site will allow people with motion limitation to enjoy longer visits; this may

lead to the creation of new paths or new restaurants' features; maybe a new kind of dedicated parking lots or renewed energy production technology.

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Introduction

The “WP4 - FreeWheel service and digital touchpoints design” aims at designing and implementing the service in all its component using the work previously achieved in WP2 - Human centred requirements and objectives and in coordination with the outputs of WP3 - FreeWheel product design.

Specifically, in the previous Work Package 2, some key outcomes have been achieved in understanding the perspectives, the unsatisfied needs and the behaviours of prospect clients, then transforming that knowledge into technical intention and commitment. Cornerstones in the design of the human-centred approach, we collected incremental knowledge with:

- D2.2 - FreeWheel experience map: based on the stories collected from all the partners and the interviews, a list of clients' goals has been identified thus giving all the partners a more precise view on what features and requirements would be needed from a user perspective;
- D2.3 - Technical and Service Objectives and key results + KPIs: this deliverable summarized the main high-level objectives from a service and a technical point of view and helped defined some of the associated Key Results;
- D2.4 - Theory of Change: with a series of co-creation sessions, the Theory of Change of the Service and Technical solutions were defined and the main impact indicators identified to measure the social impact of the Service once implemented;
- D2.5 - Technology and service requirements list definition: a collaborative work based on the outcomes of previous deliverables led to a list of requirements and features on the Technology and the Service (see figure 1 for the Service requirements) and a process was set to continuously evolve it during the project according to the discovery made.

Service requirements list	
Build a pay-per-use model with €0.20/minute	Define the billing process (start - end - rental receipt)
	Define the full cost-of-service template for facilitating the calculation of the fee/minute
Make the subscription process abandonment rate < 60%	Enable clients wheelchair data collection
	Enable categories of disabilities data collection
	Create a paperless registration process
The training for first-time use can be done in 10 minutes	Introduce preliminary usage training info in the app
	Introduce a step-by-step guide to connect the module to the wheelchair
	Prepare the tools for guiding the module's interface installation process in the most proper way (video, instructions...)
	Let the client choose to be assisted during the interface the installation, if necessary

The service must be real-time updated on modules' availability in a specific location	
The app must provide all details to reach a customer service	The app must provide a live assistance through the smartphone (app or phone call)
The app offers a way to easily switch on/off the accompanying person mode	

Table 1: Service Requirements List

Task 4.1 and the related deliverable

The task has been focused on creating a detailed understanding of the design challenges the service must face and overcome in order to provide the most valuable experience to FreeWheel clients and satisfy the service requirements. The process is described in the following chapters.

Technical content

1. Identifying the service design challenges

A design challenge, from the service design perspective, is a specific set of features or steps that require a specific care while defining and designing. Identifying and solving the right design challenges are crucial activities for setting the success of the service.

The method we used to identify the service design challenges can be summarized in 4 steps:

1. **Service envisioning:** as the service is closely linked to the technology developed, the starting point is to share an updated vision of the service based on the insights coming from WP2 and WP3;
2. **Build the first set of design challenges** using the experience map and the service outlined during the envisioning, a series of people needs were made serving as a first set of design challenges;
3. **Refine and prioritize the identified challenges** using 4 criteria to assess the set of challenges;
4. **Check the assumptions with the target group:** the identified challenges are tested with the help of the partner representing the target group (referring to the sponsor users we have in the consortium).

1.1 Service envisioning

The first vision of the service was captured through the experience map (cf. Figure 1, from Deliverable 2.2). Since this deliverable, the following deliverables of WP2, as well as a better understanding of the technology coming from WP3, have brought new insights on how the service will be shaped.

Insight #1: the experience is more complex when the service is used for the first time. Firstly because the potential client needs to identify whether he.or.she can use the service depending on his.or.her motion limitation. Secondly, because the client needs to order and receive a custom interface to connect his.or.her wheelchair to the module. Last but not least, this is the moment where the client is trained to attach the interface that connects the module to the wheelchair and then to use the driving interface.

Insight #2: given the many challenges linked to the first time use, the service should be available for a free trial (without purchasing the customized interface) to check people's ability to use it depending on their motion limitation and avoid ordering a piece they cannot use in the end.

Insight #3: when referring to possible clients in the Theory of Change (D2.4), the scope has been extended to all people with temporary or permanent motion limitation. This means a wider set of clients compared with the initial user archetypes (D2.1) which were focused only on people with permanent motion disabilities.

Insight #4: with the Theory of Change (D2.4), we envision the presence of a trained employee on site (either FreeWheel employees or the location existing staff, trained to the use of the module). The role is to provide information about the service and assist people in using the module.

Figure 1: Experience map for the shopping mall (D2.2)

1.2 Build the first set of design challenges

Starting from the experience map and from an updated vision of the service, a team reviews every step of the client’s journey looking for challenges related to the various stakeholders around the service (see Figure 2) in the two demo scenarios: the shopping mall (indoor controlled environment) and the archeological site (outdoor harsh environment).

Figure 2: The stakeholders interacting with the service

We listed the following design challenges:

- Accommodate people according to their ability to use the service autonomously and safely or with some assistance
- Produce a customized interface fully compatible with the client’s wheelchair
- Deliver the customized interface to the clients in 2 weeks after the order
- Train clients to use the module both in manual drive and in autonomous drive

- Assist clients in the installation of the interface to make the service safe to use
- Include the Accompanying person at every stage of the experience: the Accompanying person is a key stakeholder in the service experience as it is a person that is usually present to help with obstacles
- Manage the on-the-fly booking at the rack and the booking in the advance
- Find a safe way to exit the service in emergency situations without the application and/or the controller

Four phases were distinguished to rank the identified challenges according to the stage in the experience (see Figure 3):

1. **First-time use:** we separated this phase as some of the steps to use the service only occurs during the first use of this new mobility service;
2. **Before:** all steps needed from the beginning of the registration process to reach the location and to install the module interface;
3. **During:** from the moment the interface is safely connected to the module to the end of the rental;
4. **After:** when the client finishes the rent and pay according to the rental duration.

Figure 3: The 3 + 1 phases of the service experience

The following table summarizes the first set of design challenges according to the phase in the user journey:

Challenge	First-time use only	Every use
Accommodate people according to their ability to use the service autonomously and safely or with some assistance	Yes	
Produce a customized interface fully compatible with the client's wheelchair	Yes	
Deliver the customized interface to the clients in 2 weeks after the order	Yes	
Train clients to use the module both in manual drive and in autonomous drive	Yes	
Assist clients in the installation of the interface to make the service safe to use		Depending on the level of autonomy of the user and the presence of an accompanying person

Include the Accompanying person at every stage of the experience	Yes	Depends on the autonomy and independence of the user
Manage the on-the-fly booking at the rack and the booking in the advance		Yes
Find a safe way to exit the service in emergency situations without the application and/or the controller		Only in an emergency situation

Table 2: First iteration of service design challenges

1.3 Refine and prioritize the identified challenges

The list of identified problems was screened through a series of four criteria (synthesized in Figure 4) :

- **Needs:** is this challenge addressing one (or more) of the pain-points identified during the user research phase (during the interviews of WP2)?
- **Feasibility:** can this challenge be technically achieved within the project's timeframe (demos)?
- **Interest:** can be solving this challenge have a wider impact than the project (e.g. from the Research and Innovation perspective)?
- **Relevance:** is this challenge in the scope of the demo? Challenges that are not relevant for the demo are challenges related to the part of the service that will not be tested during the demo but that is critical for the full user experience of the service.

The purpose of these criteria is to navigate more easily the set of identified challenges in the next stage of the research:

- **Needs** and **Feasibility** are validation criteria: they help filter criteria taking into account the user perspective and the timeframe of the project;
- **Interest** and **Relevance** are prioritization criteria: they help focus the effort on the challenges with a wider impact and that can be tested during the demo.

Figure 4: Four criteria to analyze the service design challenges

1.4 Check the assumptions with the target group

The challenges were analyzed with sponsor users (represented by the partner Genny Angels) in a collaborative remote session, facilitated by Keen Bull, in order to validate them and discuss any new insight (see Figure 5).

The collaborative exercise went through 5 phases:

1. Discuss and validate the updated Service Experience
2. Use cases analysis (and connected user experience) to identify service's critical issues
3. Review the list of challenges
4. Sort out the identified issues (cf. step 2) and associate them with the listed challenges
5. Analyze unsorted issues to identify new challenges

Figure 5: Extract of the co-design session with Genny Angels

The session validated all the existent challenges and reshaped some of them, creating the seeds for writing the final version of the list, available in the next section of the document.

It is important to pinpoint some of the key insights that came out of the session. They confirmed all the assumptions the project is currently taking into the account within ongoing activities and they put an accent on specific challenges. These insights can be summarized in the following list:

- Clients should be able **to test the service before registering**, without getting into a process that is potentially stressful and could lead to a final frustration if they are not able to use it because of their category of motion limitation. The service can only address **some categories of disabilities** (cf. D2.1 on user archetypes to get a first view of the scope of the service);
- The service must not interfere with normal operations people can do while using a wheelchair, as well as the basic needs (going to the bathroom, eating, interacting with people);
- The service can be the access point for some other improvements of the experience, like third-party services, as well as a way to gather data and improve the general condition of people with disabilities over time.

2. Freewheel Service Design Challenges

C1 - Correctly inform the potential client about service suitability before and during the registration process

Needs	Have clients subscribing the service only if it is suitable for them, which means compatible with their motion limitation. The purpose is to avoid pointless registration and the associated pain.
Feasibility	Information about service's accessibility can be structured and delivered before and during the registration.
Interest	Defining an evaluation protocol for shared mobility services could be scalable and open-sourced. Similar sharing services can then use the protocol to check accessibility before giving access to clients.
Relevance	The solution to this challenge can be tested during the demo when registering test clients

C2 - Deliver a customized interface fully compatible with client's wheelchair to access the service 2 weeks after registration

Needs	Make the service available for all clients, connecting existing technologies (personal wheelchair and FreeWheel module) via a custom interface designed, produced and shipped in a very short time frame
Feasibility	At this stage of the research, based on our current knowledge of the selected technology (3D modelling to manage the match between the interface and the wheelchair, additive manufacturing for producing the interface), the challenge seems feasible. It will be strongly impacted by the design of the module and the interface, that is currently in development, as well as other key factors related to logistics (location of the manufacturer, packaging and shipment to the closest location for the user, etc...)
Interest	The collaborative process to remotely design and produce the interface is going to involve the clients creating synergies between existing technologies (such as cloud-based 3D model visualization and Additive Manufacturing). This model could be easily adapted in any similar service bringing the same advantages the project is aiming to
Relevance	This part of the service will not be tested during the demo

C3 - Have the interface safely installed on the wheelchair to use the service

Needs	The service requires the interface correctly installed, to work smoothly and safely. Incorrect installation can cause damage to the unit (interface + module) and, most importantly, harm the client and other people in the location.
Feasibility	Additive Manufacturing and custom approach in designing the interface can help in dealing with this challenge; in addition, the service can be shaped to provide all feasible support to deal with this key task
Interest	Difficult to asses at this stage of the research as the interface is not yet finalized making the whole installation procedure a work-in-progress area for now
Relevance	This can be tested during the demo when connecting testers wheelchairs with the module

C4 - Design the digital interface for manually driving the module

Needs	Have accessible and effective manual controls through the smartphone application to control the motion of the wheelchair equipped with the module
Feasibility	Controlling the module in manual driving is a key feature and the consortium is equipped with all the competencies needed to achieve it; the presence of a partner sponsoring end users (Genny Angels) is a key factor in working on accessibility of the system.
Interest	At the moment the service is designing a digital controller embedded into the Android application. This is probably going to generate data about accessibility to smartphones of people with disabilities that can be useful for further studies.
Relevance	This part of the service will be tested during the demo as it is a key feature of the experience

C5 - Design the service taking into account an accompanying person

Needs	Include accompanying person in the service experience since the research done so far identified him.or.her as a key actor of the experience, especially regarding the driving both in manual and autonomous mode
Feasibility	Interactions with accompanying person can be identified and defined within the upcoming service design activities, while the current technological development status
Interest	Studying the interactions between the service, the user and the accompanying person especially regarding the autonomous driving features will result in important data that could contribute to further studies or similar developing technologies.

Relevance	This can be tested during the demo comparing the experience with and without an accompanying person
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C6 - Develop an integration enabling third-party services

Example of third-party services can be a map of the location, touristic information, a list of all shops and restaurants, etc.

Needs	Make the service attractive and effective for different types of venues as identified in the Theory of Change ideation phase (see location matrix in D2.4). For example, a mall might want to deliver help with the shopping while an archaeological site might provide tourist information
Feasibility	To be further evaluated within the service design activities (D4.2)
Interest	This could promote the birth of new services delivered via the service and generate a better user experience as well as value for the providers
Relevance	This can be tested during the demo with touristic information about Patras castle

C7 - Design proper training to drive the module both manually and autonomously, including the switching between modes

Needs	Minimize the risk of a negative first experience connected with driving a new device
Feasibility	This will be further assessed with the definition of a controlling system of the module
Interest	The benchmark will discover if the development of this kind of feature can be adopted in other services or technologies addressing the same target population
Relevance	This can be tested during the demo comparing the experience with or without training

C8 - Manage the booking interactions between the "in advance mode" and the "on-the-fly-rental"

Needs	Satisfy the 2 usage scenarios coming from different clients archetypes and venues: either booking in advance or renting directly on the rack at the location.
Feasibility	This can be achieved with different models that are going to be analysed in the next phases of the project and tuned as much as possible with the needs already discovered and to be discovered

Interest	Upcoming benchmarking will discover if the development of this kind of feature is valuable out of the project
Relevance	This will not be tested during the demo

C9 - Ensure clients safety and proper assistance in case of devices (smartphone, module) or software (application, controller) failures

Needs	Provide proper assistance in a wide variety of contexts in a technologically advanced mobility service addressed to people with disabilities
Feasibility	Development of this procedures is feasible and needed in terms of service ideation, will see a strong synergy between technical development and service ideation in the next tasks of the project.
Interest	Development of procedures in this context could be addressed to other providers offering similar services to improve their accessibility for people with disabilities.
Relevance	This will be tested during the demo with a simulation of a series of emergency situations related to technology failures

The table below summarizes the challenges and their level of relevance for the demo (simulated or fully functional):

Ref.	Design challenge	Relevance for demo
C1	Correctly inform the potential client about service suitability before and during the registration process	Simulated
C2	Deliver a customized interface fully compatible with client's wheelchair to access the service 2 weeks after registration	Not tested
C3	Have the interface safely installed on the wheelchair to use the service	Fully functional
C4	Design the digital interface for manually driving the module	Fully functional
C5	Design the service taking into account an accompanying person	Fully functional
C6	Develop an integration enabling third-party services	Partly functional

C7	Design proper training to drive the module both manually and autonomously, including the switching between modes	Fully functional
C8	Manage the booking interactions between the "in advance mode" and the "on-the-fly-rental"	Simulated
C9	Ensure clients safety and proper assistance in case of devices (smartphone, module) or software (application, controller) failures	Fully functional

Table 3: Final list of Service Design Challenges

Conclusions

Service Design Challenges synthesize all the research work done from the beginning of the project to set the field for all others WP4 tasks. They combine field and qualitative research, Theory of Change, requirements and technology state-of-the-art, so they can define what are going to be the most challenging aspects of the service definition.

The main impact of this deliverable will be on task *D4.2 Service Ideation*, putting an accent and guiding the design of the phases and features meeting the challenges. The first step is going to be a dedicated study for each challenge to define the state of the art of that specific feature outside the project. Then by matching it with the consortium's possibilities, the first set of possible solutions will be formulated. Finally, these solutions will be evaluated in the context of the service and iteratively refined and selected. This will lead to *task 4.3, Service's features implementation roadmap definition*, in which the final set of them will be defined. In *task 4.4, Digital touchpoints design, implementation and test*, the focus on interactions between the client and the service will bring a series of answers to the matching challenges.

This strong influence on WP4 is going to diffuse among all connected tasks, especially on WP3 ones, first of all, because some of the challenges are directly connected to technology, then because service and technology are developed in accordingly to the agile and human-centered design that is the central methodology used in this project.

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